

Radiant Pattern	Game	Universal Level	Variant fit	Diary Entries
Open Gate	Celeste	Safety	Single-Player	"During the gaming experience, I did not feel insecure about losing progress if I needed to interrupt the session, which is directly related to the pattern's Single-Player variant."
Open Gate	Celeste	Autonomy	Single-Player	"The game features autosaves, checkpoints, and also offers the option of manual saving via the menu."
Open Gate	Celeste	Competence	Single-Player	"At other points in the UI, the game already displays information such as total game time, number of kills, and collectibles obtained (strawberries, ribbons, etc.), which shows that this data exists and is tracked."
Adaptative Challenge	Celeste	Autonomy	Hard to Beat Variant	"In addition, each chapter has a tape (side B) that, when collected, unlocks a more difficult version of that chapter."
Adaptative Challenge	Celeste	Safety	Hard to Beat Variant	"As the game presents a high level of challenge, especially because it is a platform game that requires precision in jumps and directions, the player ends up dying frequently. In these situations, when you die, the game restarts at the save point at the beginning of the puzzle, which reduces frustration and encourages new attempts."
Adaptative Challenge	Celeste	Autonomy	Single-Player	"The player can activate features such as infinite lives, infinite energy, additional dashes, or other specific aids for certain challenges."
Companion	Celeste	Safety	Single-Player	"I felt like I was creating a real connection with the NPC, especially with Theo... The dialogues contribute a lot to building the relationship."
Adaptative Challenge	Celeste	Autonomy	Hard to Beat Variant	"The game communicates that collecting all items is not mandatory for progression."
Adaptative Challenge	God of War Ragnarok	Autonomy	Single-Player	"It has several difficulty levels ranging from story mode to "god of war" (very difficult), which further expands the classic levels ranging from easy to difficult to add an even greater range of possibilities for players who want a more trivial or even more challenging experience."
Adaptative Challenge	God of War Ragnarok	Safety	Single-Player	"An important detail to note is that in "God of War" mode, it is not possible to change the difficulty after starting the game. However, this warning is given before starting the game at this difficulty level."
Adaptative Challenge	God of War Ragnarok	Competence	Hard-to-Brat Variant	"Another way the game relates to the pattern is the possibility it offers to save fights at specific checkpoints. For example, when you fight a boss and take half of his life, but die, when you respawn, the fight resumes directly from that specific point, without losing progress. Thus, the game keeps the challenge adaptable to the player's skill level."
Companion	God of War Ragnarok	Safety	Functional/Utility Variant	"When Kratos' Companions (Atreus and Mimir) provide support for the appropriate solution when the player takes too long trying to solve a puzzle."
Adaptative Challenge	God of War Ragnarok	Safety	Single-Player	"When Kratos' Companions (Atreus and Mimir) provide support for the appropriate solution when the player takes too long trying to solve a puzzle."
Adaptative Challenge	God of War Ragnarok	Safety	Puzzle Variant	"When Kratos' Companions (Atreus and Mimir) provide support for the appropriate solution when the player takes too long trying to solve a puzzle."
Adaptative Challenge	God of War Ragnarok	Autonomy	Single-Player	"I wanted to change the difficulty to get to the final stretch quickly, as I wanted to finish the story. It was really good to be able to change the difficulty when I thought it was appropriate, because otherwise I would have given up on the game."
Progression	Metroid Dread	Competence	Single-Player	"The game clearly shows the percentage of the area explored, so I can track my progress."
Progression	Metroid Dread	Competence	Single-Player	"The mission log allows me to view recent events and revisit objectives."
Progression	Metroid Dread	Competence	Single-Player	"When I discover hidden items, I always gain equipment and increase the percentage of my actions."
Adaptative Challenge	Metroid Dread	Autonomy	Single-Player	"I was able to select the difficulty between Rookie, Normal, and Hard."
Adaptative Challenge	Metroid Dread	Autonomy	Single-Player	"I can choose how to kill enemies: missile, quick time event, or basic shot."
Adaptative Challenge	Metroid Dread	Competence	Single-Player	"I felt like a better player when I was able to defend myself through quick time events."
Adaptative Challenge	Metroid Dread	Competence	Hard to Beat Variant	"Ao morrer para o E.M.M.I., o jogo me dá dicas de como derrotar ou bloquear o ataque."
Visual Support	Metroid Dread	Competence	Single-Player	"When I die to E.M.M.I., the game gives me tips on how to defeat or block the attack."
Visual Support	Metroid Dread	Safety	Single-Player	"The map glows when there are hidden items."
Visual Support	Metroid Dread	Safety	Single-Player	"The game distinguishes which weapons I can use to access hidden areas."
Visual Support	Metroid Dread	Safety	Single-Player	"I can differentiate the parasite I'm receiving by its color."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Autonomy	Functional	"A strong case for Creative Suite because creating doesn't appear as something separate from the game, but as the basis of almost everything."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Safety	Functional	"The design helps with this because making mistakes costs little. Placing and removing blocks is quick, you can go back without any problems, and this makes it easy to experiment without fear."

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Creative Suite	Minecraft	Competence	Functional	"Command blocks, for example, allow you to create rules, events, and systems within the game itself. With them, you can make adventure maps, minigames, and automations that greatly change the experience."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Autonomy	Functional	"Data packs are a middle ground between playing normally and creating a mod. They allow you to change recipes, loot, and world rules in a more accessible way, without having to leave the game environment entirely."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Autonomy	Functional	"The community greatly expands this set of tools. Mods add new blocks, systems, and ways to play, and platforms like Modrinth and CurseForge help organize and share this content."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Autonomy	Functional	"This makes creation not just an individual endeavor, but part of a larger ecosystem, where people create tools for others to create."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Safety	Functional	"When I look at the levels of the patterns it makes sense. At the most basic level, creation does not depend on payment to exist."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Competence	Functional	"At the level of control and competence, the construction language is simple and consistent, which helps you learn by doing."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Competence	Functional	"At the social level, creating becomes a way to collaborate and recognize each other in shared worlds, whether on servers or in curated content."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Autonomy	Functional	"There is no single path I need to follow. I can spend days just building, I can focus on exploration, I can get deeply involved with automation, I can create maps for other people to play or use the world as a basis for roleplay."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Safety	Functional	"We coordinate by doing, dividing tasks (one goes to get materials for the house, another collects materials for armor, one stays behind to create a plantation), and the world becomes a truly shared place."
Open Gate	Minecraft	Safety	Single-player	"The game doesn't punish me for choosing a specific way to play."
Adaptative Challenge	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Autonomy	Single-player	"It makes it very clear, right from the difficulty selection, that the game changes not only in terms of how much damage I take or how many enemies appear."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety	Navigation	"I start playing, I see this support appearing in different ways without me having to hunt through the menu: directional marking when I want to orient myself."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety	Entities	"Icon above NPC indicating that I can talk to them."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety	Navigation	"Ink as the language of the system. For me, it's not exactly a "hint" in the sense of making things easier; it's a marker of interactivity. Without some kind of marker like this, I simply wouldn't have any way of knowing that that specific wall is climbable or of differentiating it from other walls."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety	Perceptual Lens	"That hint button that makes collectibles glow is like a highlight mode that filters relevance, even if it's very specific and not a classic vision mode."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Autonomy	Navigation	"I use my survival instinct to locate myself, see the goal, and understand what's important at that moment. Once I understand, I turn it off and go back to playing with a clean screen."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety	Entities	"It helped me that the game offers support that appears in a very straightforward way, without me having to hunt for options in the menu. Sometimes I just look and understand. The icon above the NPC tells me that I can talk to them."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety	Navigation	"The climbing tutorial appears right where I'm going to use it, on the wall, so I learn as I go. This gives me the feeling that the choice is mine."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Competence	Navigation	"When the game makes it obvious what is a climbable surface, what is the objective, and what is interaction, I put my effort into planning and executing. I think about the path, calculate the time, choose the best approach. I don't keep trying to guess what the game allows."
Companion	Teamfight Tactics	Autonomy	Cosmetic Identity	"Before the match, you choose your strategist, who is a companion that represents you during the match with purely aesthetic value and does not require any kind of care to maintain."
Companion	Teamfight Tactics	Autonomy	Narrative-Based Variant	"These characters greatly affect gameplay and are not only aesthetic, but also serve as a way for players to express their preferences in terms of gameplay, visuals, and narrative attachment."
Progression	Teamfight Tactics	Competence	Combination	"My competence was satisfied by placing pieces with the same characteristics on my board, upgrading their stars, and crafting items."